

Pressure To Stick to Traditional Gender Roles: A Focus on Women Entrepreneurs

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Abstract

Introduction: The purpose of this research is to analyse the force to adhere to traditional gender roles on women entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is defined as an individual who arranges a business assuming economic stakes in the expectancy of proceeds and profits.

Literature review: In this research researcher objectives and questions are developed. However, Entrepreneurship is the biggest challenge for women entrepreneurs nowadays.

Methodology: In this research article, the researcher has selected the primary quantitative data collection method, which is followed by a survey. The researcher has made 15 close-ended questions according to the research topic. The researcher has gathered 65 responses from this survey.

Findings: As the research article has selected the primary quantitative data collection method, therefore, data analysis technique has been obeyed by SPSS analysis.

Discussion: Based on the literature review, research questions, primary quantitative data collection method, and SPSS analysis, the researcher has concluded the discussion as well as the conclusion.

Conclusion: Like other developing countries, Indian women have businesses that are more infrequent or conduct business at a lower level.

Keywords: Gender, entrepreneurship, women entrepreneurs, challenges, policymakers

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is defined as an individual who arranges a business assuming economic stakes in the expectancy of proceeds and profits. However, Entrepreneurship is the biggest challenge for women entrepreneurs nowadays.

Figure 1: Female and male population from the year 2019 to 2021

(Source: Statista, 2023)

Figure 1 shows the female and male population from the year 2019 to 2021. As per the data, in the year 2021, India registered a higher national percentage of men than that of women. Approximately half of the mannish inhabitants age between 15 and 49 years corresponded to just 41 per cent of their female partners. The gender academic gap also stayed apparent in rustic India, with just one out of three women in this province. As stated by Strawser, Hechavarría & Passerini (2021), despite

their actions and proficiency, female entrepreneurs usually fight a lot more than they usually fight their male partners to complete it great and obtain identification within the trade environment. As per the data, there are 100 entrepreneurs in India, and only 7 are female, called the Mastercard Index of Women Entrepreneurs. Chitra Gurnani Daga, CEO as well as co-founder of Thrillophilia.com is one of the most successful women entrepreneurs in India.

Research aims

The research aim is to analyse the force to adhere to traditional gender roles on women entrepreneurs.

Research objectives

RO1: To analyse the significance of female entrepreneurs in businesses entrepreneurship

RO2: To evaluate the issues have faced female entrepreneurs in business in India

RO3: To find out the function of policymakers to provide supports women entrepreneurs

RO4: To empathise with the effects of SME-related approaches for successful women-owned businesses

Research questions

RQ1: What is the significance of women entrepreneurs in businesses entrepreneurship?

RQ2: What are the issues have faced women entrepreneurs in businesses?

RQ3: What is the function of policymakers to provide supports women entrepreneurs?

RQ4: How do SME-related approaches effect successful women-owned businesses?

Literature review

Like other developing countries, Indian women have more infrequent businesses or conduct business at a lower level. As stated by Adom & Anambane (2020), obtaining women entrepreneurs into the marketplace provides more prosperous enterprises. Women have given to financial evolution while they are capable to create more trades catering to various places from their male partners. According to Selamat & Endut (2020), women entrepreneurs have supported other females living in deprivation. This has helped in decreasing deprivation and clearing obstacles. Women earning revenues bring a societal position and support autonomy. As per the data source, Khushboo Jain, co-founder of Impactguru.com, has brought changes in the social position of women as well as supported autonomy. The extent of women entrepreneurs is beneficial as females are parents and they help kids to eradicate youth deprivation. Thus, they sustain financial growth as well as development. On the other hand, as argued by Gupta & Etzkowitz (2021), women entrepreneurs usually have followed a traditional approach. They are creative, though someone's do not acknowledge them and assume their assertions to be difficult to support, discerning a defeat threat.

Despite that, females resume creating inventions by discovering ways to elevate themselves via constant education as well as acquiring suitable backgrounds. As commented by Tlaiss & McAdam (2021), while suspending relative life as well as business has been defaulting, females persist and manipulate both their residence circumstances as well as their employment with soaring colourings. This significance for creation is particularly accurate among those who profited from the recommendation of a trading trainer. However, several challenges are faced by women entrepreneurs in business in India. As argued by Maseda *et al.* (2022), despite the approaches and standards to encourage gender equivalency, males still overpower the entrepreneurial ecosystem of India. According to a data source, considerable women-owned enterprises in the nation perform in inferior-revenue sectors, while males possess additional advantageous sectors such as construction, manufacturing, and so on.

The mannish-centric essence of many enterprises also has caused women entrepreneurs to perform in sectors that are described as women-friendly, such as clothing, education, and magnificence upkeep. It has determined their knowledge, possibilities, as well as qualifications for meaningful measurement. As demonstrated by Jaim (2021), most female enterprise proprietors have not gotten the social permission they need to create their trades from families as well as immediate ecosystems. Lack of guidance from the business district is also one of the major issues faced by women entrepreneurs in India. On the other hand, as commented by Wang & Keane (2020), poor funding is one of the most considerable issues have faced female entrepreneurs in India. India, as a developing country, has poor resources of money. Therefore, this is the biggest issue for businesses.

Methodology

Data Collection Method

In this research article, the researcher has selected the primary quantitative data collection method, which is followed by a survey. As stated by Mustafa *et al.* (2021), in the survey methodology, surveys are generally engaged for the data collection from a large numeral of participants. Focus collections have been employed to construct statements as well as discernment from a mixed group of people, while obedience can produce a comprehension of the manners of individuals or groups in pragmatic environments.

In this study, the researcher has made 15 close-ended questions according to the research topic. 65 responses have been gathered by the researcher from this survey.

Data analysis technique

As the research article has selected the primary quantitative data collection method, therefore, data analysis technique has been obeyed by SPSS analysis. According to Khan (2020), SPSS is a software program commonly operated for statistical analysis. It permits data analysis for descriptive statistics, several results as well as developments projections and forecasts for determination levels.

Findings

Demographic analysis

What is your age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
	1	1.5	1.5	1.5
Valid 20-30 years	6	9.2	9.2	10.8
31-40 years	12	18.5	18.5	29.2
41-50 years	32	49.2	49.2	78.5
51-60 years	14	21.5	21.5	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

What is your gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	39	60.0	60.0	60.0
Male	9	13.8	13.8	73.8
Prefer not to say	17	26.2	26.2	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

What is your income level

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Above Rs. 100,000	13	20.0	20.0	20.0
Rs. 20,000 - Rs. 50,000	3	4.6	4.6	24.6
Valid Rs. 50,000 - Rs. 80,000	15	23.1	23.1	47.7
Rs. 80,000 - Rs. 100,000	34	52.3	52.3	100.0
Total	65	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
DV	65	4	1	5	4.03	1.045	1.093	.749	.586
IV 1	64	4	1	5	4.16	1.057	1.118	3.216	.590
IV 2	65	4	1	5	3.74	.957	.915	.567	.586
IV 3	65	4	1	5	3.77	1.247	1.555	-1.118	.586
IV 4	65	4	1	5	3.54	1.200	1.440	-1.121	.586
Valid N (listwise)	64								

From the above table the researcher has been gotten the mean of DV is 4.03, IV1 is 4.16, IV2 is 3.74, IV3 is 3.77 and IV4 is 3.54. Therefore, the relationship between DV and IV shows great associations of each other.

Regression

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.280 ^a	.079	.064	1.012	2.228

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV 1

b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.416	1	5.416	5.292	.025 ^b
	Residual	63.444	62	1.023		
	Total	68.859	63			

a. Dependent Variable: DV

b. Predictors: (Constant), IV 1

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.894	.517		5.602	.000
	IV 1	.277	.121	.280	2.301	.025

a. Dependent Variable: DV

From table 4.2, it has been showed that the value of the adjusted R square is 0.064 and the R square is 0.079 and a Durbin-Watson value of 2.228. Hence, the adjusted R-squared value shows a bit of distinction between the real and forecasted results.

Regression

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.430 ^a	.185	.172	.951	2.025

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV 2

b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.937	1	12.937	14.299	.000 ^b
	Residual	57.001	63	.905		
	Total	69.938	64			

a. Dependent Variable: DV

b. Predictors: (Constant), IV 2

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.274	.479		4.742	.000
	IV 2	.470	.124	.430	3.781	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

From the above table, it has shown the R square is 0.185 and adjusted R square value is 0.172 respectively. Therefore, it has been stated that there is a strong inter-linkage between DV and IV 2.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.449 ^a	.202	.189	.941	2.263

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV 3

b. Dependent Variable: DV

Regression

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.099	1	14.099	15.907	.000 ^b
	Residual	55.840	63	.886		
	Total	69.938	64			

a. Dependent Variable: DV

b. Predictors: (Constant), IV 3

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.612	.374		6.978	.000
	IV 3	.376	.094	.449	3.988	.000

a. Dependent Variable: DV

From the above table, it has shown the R square is 0.202 and adjusted R square value is 0.189 respectively. Therefore, it has been stated that there is a strong inter-linkage between DV and IV3.

Regression

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.248 ^a	.062	.047	1.021	2.159

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV 4

b. Dependent Variable: DV

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	4.307	1	4.307	4.135	.046 ^b
Residual	65.631	63	1.042		
Total	69.938	64			

a. Dependent Variable: DV

b. Predictors: (Constant), IV 4

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.266	.397		8.227	.000
	IV 4	.216	.106	.248	2.033	.046

a. Dependent Variable: DV

From the above table, it has shown the R square is 0.62 and adjusted R square value is 0.047 respectively. Therefore, it has been stated that there is a strong inter-linkage between DV and IV4.

Correlation

Correlations

		DV	IV 1	IV 2	IV 3	IV 4
DV	Pearson Correlation	1	.280*	.430**	.449**	.248*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.025	.000	.000	.046
	N	65	64	65	65	65
IV 1	Pearson Correlation	.280*	1	.352**	.182	.603**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.025		.004	.150	.000
	N	64	64	64	64	64
IV 2	Pearson Correlation	.430**	.352**	1	.708**	.356**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.004		.000	.004
	N	65	64	65	65	65
IV 3	Pearson Correlation	.449**	.182	.708**	1	.084
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.150	.000		.504
	N	65	64	65	65	65
IV 4	Pearson Correlation	.248*	.603**	.356**	.084	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.046	.000	.004	.504	
	N	65	64	65	65	65

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

□

From the above table, it has been stated that the correlation value is greater than 0.05 that shows a heavy relationship between IVs and DV.

Reliability

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.733	5

Discussion

Based on the literature review, research questions, primary quantitative data collection method and SPSS analysis, the researcher has concluded the discussion. As commented by Shastri, Shastri & Pareek (2019), women have given to financial evolution while they are capable to create more trades catering to various places from their male partners. Women entrepreneurs have supported other females living in deprivation. This has helped in decreasing deprivation and clearing obstacles. On the other hand, as opposed to Pritchard, Mackenzie Davey & Cooper (2019), women entrepreneurs usually have followed a traditional approach. They are creative, though someone do not acknowledge them and assume their assertions difficult to support, discerning a defeat threat.

There are various issues faced by female entrepreneurs in the business environment of India. Most of the issues have faced the female entrepreneurs are lack of guidance from the business district is also one of the major issues have faced women entrepreneurs in India. Policymakers have an influential impact on the success of women entrepreneurs' businesses.

Conclusion

From the above analysis, it can be concluded that there is a relation between the developed independent as well as dependent variables associated with the research topic. It has been observed that implicating innovative and effective methodological approaches are helpful in completing the research topic in a cohesive manner. Moreover, to extract the informational key data the researcher has selected the primary quantitative data collection method which is followed by a survey with 65 respondents. In addition to this, all the gathered data from the survey has been analysed by implicating an analytical tool SPSS to support the research aim and objective.

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